

**EFFECTS OF METHANOL EXTRACT OF *TELFAIRIA*
OCCIDENTALIS ON GLUCOSE AND BETA CELL FUNCTION IN
STREPTOZOTOCIN-INDUCED DIABETIC MALE WISTAR RATS**

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**BEING THE PROJECT REPORT SUBMITTED TO THE
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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that OJO, Timilehin Samuel, carried out this project report with matriculation number 17/46KB113. It has been read and approved as required in partial fulfillment of the award of Bachelor of Science (B.Sc) in Physiology, Department of Physiology, Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, College of Health Sciences, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria.

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this project report to the only wise God, who has been my Source and Sustainer all through my B.Sc. program. To my loving and caring parents and siblings, whose support cannot be quantified in words. And, also to my brethren and friends whose support has kept me going. And to those who have contributed, in one way or another, to make this work successful.

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ABSTRACT

Telfairia occidentalis (TO) is a grown vegetable plant with reported hypoglycemic and anti-diabetic potential. However, there is little or no information on the mechanism underlying the plant's anti-diabetic effect. This study was designed to investigate further the anti-diabetic effect of the methanol extract of *Telfairia occidentalis* (METO) in streptozotocin-induced diabetes. Diabetes was induced with streptozotocin (STZ) of 50mg/kg. Twenty-five (25) male Wistar rats were recruited and randomly divided into five (5) groups of five (5) rats each. Group A and B rats were given 1ml/kg of distilled water orally, while the diabetic rats (Groups C, D, and E) were treated with 5mg/kg of Glibenclamide, 200mg/kg of METO, and 600mg/kg of METO, respectively, for 7 days. At the end of the treatment, the rats were sacrificed, and blood samples and a liver homogenate were collected for the estimation of some biochemical parameters. 5mg/kg, 200 mg/kg, and 600 mg/kg of glibenclamide, and 200mg/kg, 600 mg/kg, and 1200 mg/kg of METO significantly reduced fasting plasma insulin levels in treated diabetic rats. Also, 5mg/kg of glibenclamide and 200 mg/kg of METO significantly increased the insulin sensitivity index in the treated diabetic rats. Still, no significant increase was observed in the diabetic rats treated with 600 mg/kg of METO. The results suggested that METO mediated changes that increased insulin sensitivity in tissues by upregulating glucose receptors, thereby increasing glucose utilization via insulin action on the receptors.

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Diabetes mellitus is an epidemic occurring in adults throughout the world and is the leading cause of kidney failure, heart attack, blindness, and lower limb amputation. It is the fourth leading cause of death in most developed countries. The prevalence of diabetes is estimated to reach 330 million by the year 2025, according to the International Diabetes Federation, with the most significant potential increase being in Africa and Asia. This numerical increase will occur in developing countries. Thus, by 2025, over 75% of people with diabetes will reside in developing countries, compared with 62% in 1995 (Hillary et al., 1998). In Nigeria, it is the most common endocrine disease. In the past, it was believed that insulin would wipe out diabetes. Unfortunately, it has been established that neither insulin (hormonal) injection nor any other antidiabetic drug on the market restores normal glycemic control (Francois, 1998; Marshal et al., 1998). Moreover, the World Health Organization (WHO) estimates that 80% of people in developing countries depend on traditional medicine for their health needs, and that 85% of traditional medicine uses plant extracts. In other words, about 4 billion people in the world rely on plants as a source of drugs. This has led researchers to continue their search for an “efficacious drug” for the treatment of diabetes.

Fluted gourd or pumpkin, also called *Telfairia occidentalis* (TO), is an evergreen food crop widely cultivated in many West African regions, mainly in Sierra Leone and the Southern parts of Nigeria, for its nutritional and medicinal uses.

It has been reported that TO can be used to treat anemia, convulsion, atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease, high blood pressure, hypercholesterolemia, arthritis, liver problems, and inflammatory conditions (Oyolu, 1978; Ajayi et al., 2000; Alada, 2000; Oboh, 2005; Iwu, 1983; Oluwole et al., 2003).

Until recently, the effects of TO on blood glucose have been controversial, with some studies reporting a reduction (Aderibigbe *et al.*, 1999; Eseyin *et al.*, 2000; Emudianughe & Aderibigbe, 2002; Nwozo *et al.*, 2004; Salman *et al.*, 2008; Eseyin *et al.*, 2010; Eseyin *et al.*, 2014) while others reported an increase in blood glucose (Adisa *et al.*, 2012) following short-term and long-term treatment, respectively. Salman *et al.* (2013) recently reported a decrease in blood glucose after 1 week of TO treatment, followed by an increase after 2 weeks.

1.2 JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

Salman *et al.* (2013) reported a decrease in blood glucose after 1 week of TO treatment, followed by an increase after 2 weeks. While Salman *et al.* (2013) reported that the blood glucose-lowering effect of TO observed after one week of treatment could be insulin-dependent as the authors observed an increase in plasma insulin while plasma insulin returned to normal after two weeks of treatment following an increase in blood glucose, the mechanism(s) involved in the increased blood glucose following two weeks of treatment with TO remains poorly understood. There is little or no information on the tissue's responsiveness to insulin.

This project was undertaken to determine the effect of *Telfairia occidentalis* on fasting plasma glucose, plasma insulin, and the insulin sensitivity index, and to understand beta-cell function in diabetic cases as a whole.

1.3 AIM OF THE STUDY

The present study was designed to investigate the effects of the methanol extract of *Telfairia occidentalis* on plasma glucose, plasma insulin, and insulin sensitivity index.

1.4 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The specific objectives of the present study include;

- 1) To evaluate the effect of the methanol extract of *Telfairia occidentalis* leaves on fasting plasma glucose in male Wistar rats.
- 2) To evaluate the effect of the methanol extract of *Telfairia occidentalis* leaves on plasma insulin in male Wistar rats.
- 3) To investigate the impact of *Telfairia occidentalis* on the insulin sensitivity index.
- 4) To evaluate the effect of *Telfairia occidentalis* on the liver–total body weight ratio.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Fluted gourd or pumpkin, also called *Telfairia occidentalis*, is an evergreen food crop widely cultivated in many West African regions, mainly in Sierra Leone and the East/South-South parts of Nigeria, for its nutritional and medicinal uses. The leaves and seeds are the most widely consumed parts as a vegetable and an oil source, respectively, and the plant's pharmacological activities have been extensively reviewed (Aworunse *et al.*, 2018).

Some pharmacological activities of TO leaves and seeds include anti-plasmodial (Okokon *et al.*, 2009), antihypertensive (Oboh *et al.*, 2016), anti-anaemic (Salman *et al.*, 2018), and antioxidant (Ironi *et al.*, 2017) activities. While the leaves are a rich source of carbohydrates (sucrose), ascorbic acid, and polyphenols, the seeds contain high levels of betaglobulin proteins and oils, mainly monounsaturated fatty acids (Akintayo, 1997).

The hypoglycaemic effect of TO leaf extracts has been well-documented (Eseyin *et al.*, 2007). A single administration of TO leaf extracts acutely reduced fasting blood glucose in fasted alloxan-induced diabetic animals (Eseyin *et al.*, 2010), while the repeated administration reduced fasting blood glucose in normoglycaemic animals (Salman *et al.*, 2008) and diabetic animals (Nwozo *et al.*, 2004).

Previous studies (Salman *et al.*, 2013; Salman *et al.*, 2020) have attributed the blood-glucose-lowering effect to an increase in plasma insulin following TO treatment.

Figure 1: Picture of Telfaria occidentalis leaves (GlobalFoodBook.com, 2015)

2.1 BOTANICAL CLASSIFICATION OF *TELFAIRIA OCCIDENTALIS*

Integrated Taxonomy Information System gave the taxonomic hierarchy of *Telfairia occidentalis* as follows:

Kingdom (*Plantae*– plants),

Subkingdom (*Viridaeplantae* – green plants),

Infrakingdom (*Streptophyta* – land plants),

Division (*Tracheophyta* – vascular plants, tracheophytes),

Subdivision (*Spermatophytina* – spermatophytes, seed plants),

Infradivision (*Angiospermae* – flowering plants, angiosperms),

Class (*Magnoliopsida*),

Superorder (*Rosanae*),

Order (*Cucurbitales*),

Family (*Cucurbitaceae* – gourds),

Genus (*Telfairia* Hook.),

Species (*Telfairia occidentalis* Hook. foysternut).

Taxonomic Serial No.: 505897 (Obeagu *et al.*, 2014).

2.2 STRUCTURE OF TELFAIRIA OCCIDENTALIS

The fluted gourd fruit is quite large; one study documented a range of 16–105 centimetres. (6.3–41.3 in) in length, and an average of 9 cm in diameter (Okoli & Mgbeogu, 1983). The same study found that seed counts in larger gourds reached upwards of 196 per fruit, typically measuring 3.4-4.9 cm in length (Okoli & Mgbeogu, 1983). In both the pistillate and staminate varieties, *T. occidentalis* flowers grow in sets of five, with creamy-white and dark red petals, contrasting with the light green colour of the fruit when young, and yellow when ripe (Okoli & Mgbeogu, 1983). Dioecious flowering is most common in the fluted gourd, with very few documented cases of monoecious flowering.

2.3 CHEMICAL COMPOSITION

Crude fiber content of $20.17 \pm 0.12\%$ in the leaves of *Telfairia occidentalis* indicated that the leaves of this plant are good sources of dietary fibers compared to the RDA. A higher carbohydrate content of $39.64 \pm 0.01\%$ led to a corresponding increase in energy value, recorded as 290.16 ± 0.03 Kcal/100g, further confirming that these plant leaves could serve as a good source of energy. Mineral composition give the result as K (2760.05 ± 0.02 mg/100g), Cu (1.72 ± 0.01 mg/100g), Fe (15.64 ± 0.04 mg/100g), Mn (15.71 ± 0.01 mg/100g), Mg (76.46 ± 0.02 mg/100g) and Mg (5.52 ± 0.02 mg/100g) which indicated that the leaves of *Telfairia occidentalis* are good sources of K, Cu, Fe and Mn, moderate sources of Mg and Zn when compared to their RDA. They are essential in human and animal nutrition. (Idris, 2012).

2.4 CULTIVATION

T. occidentalis is typically grown vertically on trestle-like structures; however, it can be allowed to spread flat on a field (Okoli & Mgbeogu, 1983). A beneficial outcome of growing the gourd flat is the suppression of weeds, especially when intercropped with a tall, upright plant such as maize. The growing period begins in April or May when seeds are planted (Nwufo & Emebiri, 1990). The first leaves and shoots can be harvested after a month and can be collected every 2–4 weeks thereafter. Seeds are planted directly in the soil, typically in groups of three to increase output in case of a failed germination (Akoroda, 1990). Fruit is typically harvested between October and December

(Aiyelaagbe and Kintomo, 2002). The seeds are subsequently collected and dried; a portion is consumed, while the remainder is stored for the following planting season. Although dependent upon soil type, the fluted gourd can ratoon and subsequently produce many flushes of fruit over long periods. It can root with the highest degree of success in well-drained soils (Akoroda, 1990). It is propagated using the seeds. Its seed is housed in another, larger covering or hard shell that protects it from harm. It survives drought and can retain its life in the root even after many years. It is a creeping plant and grows well if staked with bamboo sticks.

2.5 STORAGE

Although the seeds of *T. occidentalis* store well, precautions must be taken when storing any portion of the plant, particularly if the gourd is to be stored whole. This is not a typical storage method, as the fluted gourd pod (the fruit itself) is highly perishable and can be stored for only 4 weeks (Nwufu & Emebiri, 1990). If the gourd is left intact and proper storage and shipping are not practiced, pod rot can develop from small lesions and cause severe damage to the entire fruit, rendering it unusable (Nwufu & Emebiri, 1990). Furthermore, care must be taken when storing the leaves, which rapidly lose nutritional and water content when stored improperly (Nwufu, 1994). These losses can be reduced by storing harvested leaves in sealed, polyethylene bags, as well as at lower temperatures (2-4 °C) (Nwufu, 1994)

2.6 MEDICINAL VALUES OF *TELFAIRIA OCCIDENTALIS*

2.6.1 FLUTED PLUMPKIN BOOSTS BLOOD LEVEL AND BEATS DIABETES

In Nigeria, the herbal preparation of the plant has been used to treat anaemia, chronic fatigue, and diabetes (Adedapo *et al.*, 2021). Anaemia constitutes a serious health problem in many tropical countries because of the prevalence of malaria and other parasitic infections. In anaemia, the circulating haemoglobin level is decreased, below 13 g dL⁻¹ in males and 12 g dL⁻¹ in females (Okochi *et al.*, 2003). In the tropics, where malaria is endemic, between 10 and 20% of the population has haemoglobin levels below 10 g dL⁻¹. Children are more vulnerable. The leaves are rich in iron and play a key role in the treatment of anaemia; they are also noted for their lactating properties and are in high demand among nursing mothers (Okoli & Mgbeogu, 1983).

Type 2 diabetes is associated with increased oxidative stress, which probably results from both excess generation of reactive oxygen species and decreased antioxidant defenses (Baynes, 1991; Tribe and Poston, 1996) Aqueous extracts of *Telfairia occidentalis* had been reported to reduce blood glucose level and also have antidiabetic effects in glucose induced hyperglycemic and streptozotocin (STZ) induced diabetic mice (AderIbigbe *et al.*, 1999), while it did not alter the glucose levels in normoglycemic mice. Salman *et al.* (2008) also reported reduced blood glucose levels in male rats treated with *Telfairia occidentalis* leaves. Hypoglycemic effects have also been reported by many researchers (Aderibigbe *et al.*, 1999; Eseyin *et al.*, 2000, 2005c, 2007; Nwozo *et al.*, 2004).

2.6.2 GENERAL HEALTH BENEFITS OF *TELFAIRIA OCCIDENTALIS*

Telfairia occidentalis is an important staple vegetable grown in Nigeria. The plant produces luxuriant, edible green leaves that are rich in iron and vitamins. The plants have long, twisting tendrils and leaves divided into three to five leaflets, with the terminal leaflets up to 15 cm long. The male plant is grown principally for leaves and seeds, which are important soup ingredients. Recent studies have shown that *Telfairia occidentalis* leaves are rich in minerals (such as iron, potassium, sodium, phosphorus, calcium, and magnesium), antioxidants, vitamins (such as thiamine, riboflavin, nicotinamide, and ascorbic acid), and phytochemicals, including phenols. Harvesting of fluted pumpkin takes place 120-150 days after sowing (Ajibade *et al.*, 2006; Kayode *et al.*, 2009). The leaves contain essential oils and vitamins; the root contains cucurbitacin, sesquiterpenes, and lactones (Iwu, 1983). The young leaves, sliced and mixed with coconut water and salt, are stored in a bottle and used in ethnomedicine to treat convulsions (Gbile, 1986). The leaf extract is helpful in the management of cholesterolaemia, liver problems, and impaired immune defense systems (Eseyin *et al.*, 2005). The roots are used as rodenticides and as ordeal poisons (Gill, 1992). The essential amino acid contents compared favorably with those of important legumes (Asiegbu, 1987). The amino acid profile of TO has also been shown to be very rich, including alanine, aspartate, glycine, glutamine, histidine, lysine, methionine, tryptophan, cystine, leucine, arginine, serine, threonine, phenylalanine, valine, tyrosine, and isoleucine (Tindall, 1968; Fasuyi, 2006). Emeka and Obidoa (2009) study

reveals that the long term feeding of TOsupplemented diet caused a significant increase in weight of animals which may be due to its content of rich nutrients.

The seeds are highly nutritious and are roasted or boiled and eaten like breadfruit (*Treculia*) seeds; they are also sometimes used as soup thickeners (Okoli & Mbeagwu, 1983). The seed is very rich in oil, mainly unsaturated acids, which form 61% of the oil (Nyanayo, 1988; Odoemena & Onyeneke, 1998). Akubue *et al.* (1980) and Taylor *et al.* (1983) have documented that fluted pumpkin seeds are a good source of four minerals required in human nutrition. The report showed that the seed contained 29% oil and 30% protein. Asiegbu (1987) reported that fluted pumpkin seed contains 47% oil and 31% protein. The protein was reported to be markedly deficient in sulfur-containing amino acids. Longe *et al.* (1983) reported that fluted plumpkin seeds had 53% fat, 22% protein, 3% fibre, 15% carbohydrates, and 2% ash. Oyolu (1980) observed that vegetables will continue to remain the primary source of proteins, minerals and vitamins in African countries, he noted that leaves and edible shoots of fluted pumpkin together contain 85% moisture, while the dry portion of what is usually consumed contains 11% crude protein, 25% carbohydrate, 3% oil, 11% ash and as much as 700 ppm iron. The results of the study carried out by Christian (2007) show that the seed contains essential nutrients in significant amounts that can supplement other foods. The levels of crude protein (3.47%), crude fat (31.38%), moisture (10.93), Ash (2.02%), carbohydrate (50.08%), fibre (2.12%), calcium (280 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$), phosphorus (2100 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$), iron (69 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$), sodium (10.80 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$), potassium (1280 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$), vitamin A (890 IU) and vitamin C (0.7 $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$) detected in the seed were compared with

nutritional composition of some plant foods in Nigeria. The study shows that the seed of *Telfairia occidentalis* is high in carbohydrates, fat, and phosphorus. The seed also contained levels of vitamin A, which can supplement other dietary sources. The oil from *Telfairia occidentalis* seeds has a higher iodine value than palm oil, indicating a higher content of unsaturated fatty acids. This suggests that it may be used as an edible oil for cooking or for the manufacture of margarine (Christian, 2007).

The high protein content in the leaves of plants such as TO could serve as a supplementary source of protein for the body's daily requirements. The symptoms of protein-energy malnutrition, such as Kwashiorkor and Marasmus, were rarely observed among dwellers in regions where adequate protein is obtained from fruits/seeds, and leaves of plants rich in protein, such as TO (Kayode *et al.*, 2009; Kayode *et al.*, 2010). Fasuyi and Nonyerem's (2007) investigations showed that *Telfairia occidentalis* leaf meal caused increased growth in birds. Adaramoye *et al.* (2007) reported that *Telfairia occidentalis* leaves have a *hypolipidaemic effect and may be a valuable therapy for hypercholesterolaemia*. This confirms the research work of Eseyin *et al.* (2005). Williams *et al.* (2009) investigated the vitamin A content and consumption patterns of some green leafy vegetables (including *Telfairia occidentalis*) among pregnant women in Calabar, Nigeria. They observed that *Telfairia occidentalis* has the highest vitamin A content, which is adequate to meet their vitamin A requirement (Williams *et al.*, 2009). The fruits of *Telfairia occidentalis* have been utilized in the production of marmalade (Egbekun *et al.*, 1998). The use of *Telfairia occidentalis* in traditional medicine for reproduction and fertility is gradually attracting

interest in medical science. A study by Nwangwu and colleagues showed that *Telfairia occidentalis* has the potential to regenerate testicular tissue and increase spermatogenesis (Nwangwu *et al.*, 2007). However, further research is required to confirm this observation.

2.6.3 ANTIOXIDANT AND FREE RADICAL SCAVENGING PROPERTY

Almost all organisms possess antioxidant defense and repair systems that evolved to protect them against oxidative damage; however, these systems are insufficient to prevent them entirely. However, antioxidant supplements or foods containing antioxidants may help the body reduce oxidative damage (Yang *et al.*, 2002).

The darkish green leafy vegetable leaves of *Telfairia occidentalis* and extracts (such as aqueous and ethanol extracts) from the leaves have been found to suppress or prevent the production of free radicals and scavenge already produced free radicals, lower lipid peroxidation status, and elevate antioxidant enzymes (such as superoxide dismutase and Catalase) both *in vitro* and *in vivo* (Oboh *et al.*, 2004, 2006; Adaramoye *et al.*, 2007; Nwanna and Oboh (2007). Emeka and Obidoa, 2009; Kayode *et al.*, 2009; Kayode *et al.*, 2010). *Telfairia occidentalis* has also been found to protect and ameliorate oxidative brain and liver damage induced by malnutrition in rats (Kayode *et al.*, 2009, 2010). Nwanna and Oboh (2007) reported the hepatoprotective property of polyphenol extracts of

Telfairia occidentalis leaves on acetaminophen-induced liver damage. Oboh (2005) reported that both aqueous and ethanolic extracts of TO leaves protect liver cells against garlic-induced oxidative damage. However, the aqueous extract is more effective than the

ethanol extract, which could be attributed to the higher antioxidant activity of the aqueous extract of TO leaves. Hepatoprotective effects of *Telfairia occidentalis* leaves have been reported by Eseyin *et al.* (2005), Emeka and Obidoa (2009), and Kayode *et al.* (2010).

Researchers have observed free radical-scavenging activity and antioxidant properties in *Telfairia occidentalis* (Kayode *et al.*, 2010). Their antioxidant effect is attributed to the presence of vitamins and phenolic compounds, such as flavonoids and tannins, which are both forms of polyphenols (Halliwell & Gutteridge, 1999). Phenolic compounds can protect the human body from free radicals, whose formation is associated with the normal metabolism of aerobic cells. They are potent antioxidants capable of removing free radicals, chelating metal catalysts, activating antioxidant enzymes, reducing α -tocopherol radicals, and inhibiting oxidases (Oboh & Rocha, 2007).

Polyphenols are considered potent antioxidants due to the redox properties of their hydroxyl groups (Oboh & Rocha, 2007). In addition to their role as free radical scavengers, they also form complexes with reactive metals such as zinc, iron, and copper to reduce their absorption. At first glance, this may seem to be an adverse side effect.

(reducing nutrient absorption), However, excess levels of such elements in the body can promote the generation of free radicals and contribute to oxidative damage of cell membranes and cellular DNA. Numerous studies have conclusively shown that the majority of the antioxidant activities in plants may be due to flavonoids rather than vitamin C, E, and β -carotene (Rong, 2010), which are micronutrient antioxidants present in TO leaves.

2.6.4 EFFECT OF *TELFAIRIA OCCIDENTALIS* ON BLOOD GLUCOSE LEVEL AND DIABETES

In Nigeria, the herbal preparation of the plant has been employed in the treatment of anaemia, chronic fatigue, and diabetes (Aderibigbe *et al.*, 1999; Alada, 2000; Dina *et al.*, 2006). Anaemia constitutes a serious health problem in many tropical countries because of the prevalence of malaria and other parasitic infections. In anaemia, the circulating haemoglobin level is decreased, below 13 g/dl in males and 12 g/dl in females (Okochi *et al.*, 2003). In the tropics, where malaria is endemic, between 10 and 20% of the population has haemoglobin levels below 10 g/dl (Diallo *et al.*, 2008). Children are more vulnerable. The leaves are rich in iron and play a key role in the treatment of anaemia; they are also noted for their lactating properties and are in high demand among nursing mothers (Okoli & Mgbeogu, 1983).

Type 2 diabetes is associated with increased oxidative stress, likely due to both excess reactive oxygen species production and decreased antioxidant defenses (Baynes, 1991; Tribe & Poston, 1996). In recent years, it has been shown that the most important factor in increasing free radical production in diabetes is hyperglycaemia, which can induce mitochondrial superoxide overproduction (Brownlee, 2001). Superoxide is converted to hydroxyl radicals, which can diffuse across membranes and initiate lipid peroxidation. The oxidation of unsaturated lipids has implications not only for atherosclerosis but also for the stability and integrity of the red cell membranes (Steinberg *et al.*, 1989). Increased lipid peroxidation, as evidenced by breakdown products such as malondialdehyde, has been

observed in erythrocytes and plasma from type 2 diabetic patients. Supplementation with antioxidants is, therefore, an attractive potential therapy. Aqueous extracts of *Telfairia occidentalis* have been reported to reduce blood glucose levels and to have antidiabetic effects in glucose-induced hyperglycemic and streptozotocin (STZ)- induced diabetic mice. At the same time, they did not alter glucose levels in normoglycemic mice (Aderibigbe *et al.*, 1999). Salman *et al.* (2008) also reported reduced blood glucose levels in male rats treated with *Telfairia occidentalis* leaves. Hypoglycemic effects have also been reported by many researchers (Aderibigbe *et al.*, 1999; Eseyin *et al.*, 2000).

Until recently, the effects of TO on blood glucose have been controversial, with some studies reporting a reduction (Aderibigbe *et al.*, 1999; Eseyin *et al.*, 2000; Emudianughe & Aderibigbe, 2002; Nwozo *et al.*, 2004; Salman *et al.*, 2008; Eseyin *et al.*, 2010; Eseyin *et al.*, 2014b) while others reported an increase in blood glucose (Adisa *et al.*, 2003) following short-term and long-term treatment, respectively. Salman *et al.* (2013) recently reported a decrease in blood glucose after 1 week of TO treatment, followed by an increase after 2 weeks. While Salman *et al.* (2013) reported that the blood glucose-lowering effect of TO observed after one week of treatment could be insulin-dependent, as the authors observed an increase in plasma insulin.

2.7 DIABETES MELLITUS

Diabetes mellitus is a group of metabolic diseases characterized by chronic hyperglycemia resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both.

(American Diabetes Association, 2013)

2.7.1 TYPES OF DIABETES MELLITUS

DM is broadly classified into three types by etiology and clinical presentation: type 1 diabetes, type 2 diabetes, and gestational diabetes (GDM). Some other less common types of diabetes include monogenic diabetes and secondary diabetes.

1. Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus (T1DM)

Type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM) accounts for 5% to 10% of DM and is characterized by autoimmune destruction of insulin-producing beta cells in the pancreas. As a result, there is an absolute insulin deficiency. A combination of genetic susceptibility and environmental factors, such as viral infections, toxins, or certain dietary factors, has been implicated as triggers of autoimmunity. T1DM is most commonly seen in children and adolescents, though it can develop at any age (Malek *et al.*, 2019).

2. Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM)

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) accounts for around 90% of all cases of diabetes. In T2DM, the insulin response is diminished, a condition known as insulin resistance. During this state, insulin is ineffective and is initially countered by an increase in insulin production to maintain glucose homeostasis, but over time, insulin production decreases,

resulting in T2DM. T2DM is most commonly seen in persons older than 45 years. Still, it is increasingly seen in children, adolescents, and younger adults due to rising levels of obesity, physical inactivity, and energy-dense diets (Picke *et al.*, 2019).

3. Gestational Diabetes Mellitus

Hyperglycemia, which is first detected during pregnancy, is classified as gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM), also known as hyperglycemia in pregnancy. Although it can occur anytime during pregnancy, GDM generally affects pregnant women during the second and third trimesters. According to the American Diabetes Association (ADA), GDM complicates 7% of all pregnancies. Women with GDM and their offspring have an increased risk of developing type 2 diabetes mellitus in the future.

GDM can be complicated by hypertension, preeclampsia, and hydramnios, and may also lead to increased operative interventions. The fetus can have increased weight and size (macrosomia) or congenital anomalies. Even after birth, such infants may have respiratory distress syndrome and subsequent childhood and adolescent obesity. Older age, obesity, excessive gestational weight gain, history of congenital anomalies in previous children, or stillbirth, or a family history of diabetes are risk factors for GDM (Choi & Chung, 2016).

4. Monogenic Diabetes

A single genetic mutation in an autosomal dominant gene causes this type of diabetes. Examples of monogenic diabetes include conditions like neonatal diabetes mellitus and

maturity-onset diabetes of the young (MODY). Around 1 to 5% of all diabetes cases are due to monogenic diabetes. MODY is a familial disorder and usually presents under the age of 25 years (Malek *et al.*, 2019).

5. Secondary Diabetes

Secondary diabetes is caused by the complication of other diseases affecting the pancreas (for example, pancreatitis), hormone disturbances (for example, Cushing's disease), or drugs (for example, corticosteroids (Carrillo-Larco *et al.*, 2019)).

2.7.2 SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS OF DIABETES MELLITUS

1. Unexplained weight loss
2. Frequent fatigue
3. Irritability
4. Repeated infections, especially in the Genital areas, Urinary tract, Skin, Oral cavity, and delayed wound healing
5. Dry mouth
6. Burning, pain, numbness in the feet
7. Itching
8. Reactive hypoglycemia

9. Acanthosis nigricans-the presence of velvety dark patches on the neck, armpit, and groin, which is an indicator of insulin resistance
10. Decreased vision
11. Impotence or erectile dysfunction. (Selvamuthukumaran, 2018)

2.7.3 RISK FACTORS FOR DIABETES

- Certain races/ethnicities (Native American, African American, Hispanics, or Asian American, Pacific Islander) (Kempegowda *et al.*, 2019)
- Persons older than 40 years of age (Martinez *et al.*, 2019)
- Overweight or obese persons with a BMI greater than or equal to 25 kg/m² or 23 kg/m² in Asian Americans (Thewjitcharoen *et al.*, 2018)
- First-degree relative with diabetes mellitus
- History of cardiovascular disease or hypertension (Hussain & Chowdhury, 2019)
- Low HDL-cholesterol or hypertriglyceridemia (Thewjitcharoen *et al.*, 2018)
- Women with polycystic ovarian syndrome
- Physical inactivity
- Conditions associated with insulin resistance, for example, Acanthosis nigricans

2.7.4 DIAGNOSING DIABETES MELLITUS

Diabetes mellitus is diagnosed using either plasma glucose estimation (FPG or OGTT) or HbA1c. Estimation of the cutoff values for glucose and HbA1c is based on the association between FPG or HbA1c and retinopathy. Fasting plasma glucose of ≥ 126 mg/dL (7.0 mmol/L), plasma glucose after 2-h OGTT ≥ 200 mg/dL (11.1 mmol/L), HbA1c $\geq 6.5\%$ (48 mmol/mol) or a random plasma glucose ≥ 200 mg/dL (11.1 mmol/L) along with symptoms of hyperglycemia is diagnostic of diabetes mellitus. In addition to monitor the treatment of diabetes, HbA1c has been recommended to diagnose diabetes by the International Expert Committee in 2009 (International Expert Committee Report on the Role of the A1C Assay in the Diagnosis of Diabetes, 2009) and endorsed by ADA (American Diabetes Association, 2013), the Endocrine Society, the WHO and many scientists and related organizations all over the world. The advantages and disadvantages of the different tests used to diagnose diabetes have been reviewed by Sacks et al (Sacks *et al.*, 2011)

The advantages of using HbA1c over FPG to diagnose diabetes include greater convenience and preanalytical stability, lower CV (3.6%) compared to FPG (5.7%) and two h OGTT (16.6%), stronger correlation with microvascular complications especially retinopathy, and a marker for glycemic control and glycation of proteins which is the direct link between diagnosis of diabetes and its complications (Shaw *et al.*, 2011). It is recommended that asymptomatic patients repeat the HbA1c test within 2 weeks to confirm a single apparently diagnostic result (McDonald & Warren, 2014). A cut-off value for

HbA1c of $\geq 6.5\%$ (48 mmol/mol) has been endorsed by many countries and ethnic groups, yet ethnicity appears to affect the cut-off values for diagnosing diabetes (Ma *et al.*, 2013). Cut-off values of 5.5% (37 mmol/mol) (Mukai *et al.*, 2012) and 6.5% (48 mmol/mol) (Tsugawa *et al.*, 2012) have been reported in a Japanese study, 6.0% (42 mmol/mol) in the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES III), 6.2% (44 mmol/mol) in a Pima Indian study, 6.3% (45 mmol/mol) in an Egyptian study as reported by Davidson; and three cut-off values for Chinese. The Australians recommended using two cut-off values: $\leq 5.5\%$ to “rule-out” and $\geq 7.0\%$ to “rule-in” diabetes. Variations in the prevalence of diabetes (Bernal-Lopez *et al.*, 2011) and prediabetes (Kawada, 2012) due to ethnicity have been documented. Most studies diagnosed fewer subjects with diabetes using HbA1c than using FPG or OGTT (Hayes *et al.*, 2012). Yet, other studies reported more subjects diagnosed with diabetes using HbA1c (Kharroubi *et al.*, 2014)

2.7.5 TREATMENT OF DIABETES

For both T1DM and T2DM, the cornerstone of therapy is diet and exercise (Eckstein *et al.*, 2019). A diet low in saturated fat, refined carbohydrates, and high-fructose corn syrup, and high in fiber and monounsaturated fats, needs to be encouraged. Aerobic exercise for 90 to 150 minutes per week is also beneficial. The primary target in obese T2DM patients is weight loss. If adequate glycemia cannot be achieved, metformin is the first-line therapy. Following metformin, many other therapies, such as oral sulfonylureas and dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitors, are available. Glucagon-like peptide-1

(GLP-1) receptor agonists, Sodium-glucose co-transporter-2 (SGLT2) inhibitors, pioglitazone, especially if the patient has fatty liver disease, alpha-glucosidase inhibitors, and insulin, are available (Lai *et al.*, 2019).

Recent studies have shown that the SGLT2 inhibitor empagliflozin (EMPA) and the GLP-1 receptor agonist liraglutide reduce cardiovascular (CV) events and mortality. Hence, in patients with CV disease, these drugs should be considered next. For patients with T1DM, a basal-bolus insulin regimen is the mainstay of therapy. Also, insulin pump therapy is a reasonable choice. Since hypoglycemia is associated with increased mortality, preference should be given to therapies that do not induce hypoglycemia, such as DPP-4 Inhibitors, SGLT-2 inhibitors, GLP-1 receptor agonists, and pioglitazone with metformin. The other advantages of SGLT-2 inhibitors and GLP-1 receptor agonists include reductions in body weight, blood pressure (BP), and albuminuria (Massey *et al.*, 2019).

To reduce microvascular complications in the majority, the goal Hb A1C should be less than 7%. Also, the BP goal should be less than 130/85 mmHg, with a preference for angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitor or angiotensin receptor blocker (ARB) therapy. Fundal exams should be undertaken as proposed by guidelines, and urine albumin excretion at least twice a year.

For the lipid panel, the goal is LDL-C less than 100 mg/dl if no atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease (ASCVD) is present, or less than 70 mg/dl if ASCVD is present. The drug of choice is a statin since these drugs reduce CV events and CV mortality.

Consider adding ezetimibe and PCSK9 inhibitors for patients with ASCVD who are not at goal (Shah *et al.*, 2019)

2.8 GLUCOSE

Glucose is the most important monosaccharide present in our body. It belongs to the hexose category of monosaccharides. Glucose provides energy to all cells in our bodies except cardiac myocytes. Excess glucose is stored in the body in the form of glycogen in the liver and muscles, and as triglycerides in the fat cells.

2.8.1 WHAT IS GLUCOSE?

Glucose, also called dextrose, belongs to a group of carbohydrates known as simple sugars (monosaccharides). Monosaccharides are carbohydrate molecules that cannot be broken down to simpler carbohydrate molecules by hydrolysis, so they are sometimes referred to as simple sugars. Glucose has the molecular formula $C_6H_{12}O_6$. It is found in fruits and honey and is the major free sugar circulating in the blood of higher animals. It is the source of energy in cell function, and the regulation of its metabolism is of great importance (gluconeogenesis). Molecules of starch, the primary energy-reserve carbohydrate of plants, consist of thousands of glucose units, as do those of cellulose. Also composed of glucose is glycogen, the reserve carbohydrate in most vertebrate and invertebrate animal cells, as well as those of numerous fungi and protozoans (Shendurse & Khedkar, 2016)

2.8.2 PROPERTIES OF GLUCOSE SOLUBILITY

One of the significant physical properties of glucose is its ability to dissolve in aqueous solution, that is, a water-based solution. Since blood, extracellular fluid, and intracellular fluid are all water-based, for glucose to dissolve in the bloodstream and pass into cells, it must also dissolve well in water. Compounds composed solely of carbon and hydrogen exhibit very low water solubility. Elements such as oxygen and nitrogen, which are common in organic and bioorganic molecules, help increase water solubility. Glucose's six oxygen atoms increase its ability to dissolve in water. In particular, since five of those oxygen atoms are present as alcohol groups, which readily form hydrogen bonds with water molecules, glucose dissolves quite readily in water.

2.8.3 SOURCES OF GLUCOSE

Most dietary carbohydrates contain glucose, either as their only building block (as in the polysaccharides starch and glycogen) or together with another monosaccharide (as in the heteropolysaccharides sucrose and lactose) (Chattopadhyay, 2018). Unbound glucose is one of the main ingredients of honey. Glucose is highly abundant and has been isolated from a variety of natural sources across the world, including male cones of the coniferous tree *Wollemia nobilis* in Rome (Venditti et al., 2019), the roots of *Ilex asprella* plants in China (Lei et al., 2014), and straws from rice in California (Balan et al., 2009)

2.8.4 GENERAL FUNCTIONS OF GLUCOSE

- 1) **Energy Production:** The primary role of carbohydrates is to supply energy to all cells in the body. Many cells prefer glucose as a source of energy over fatty acids. Some cells, such as red blood cells, can produce cellular energy only from glucose. The brain is also susceptible to low blood-glucose levels because it uses *only* glucose to produce energy and function (unless under extreme starvation conditions). About 70 percent of the glucose entering the body from digestion is redistributed (by the liver) back into the blood for use by other tissues.
- 2) **Energy Storage:** The excess glucose is stored as glycogen (mainly stored in the muscle and liver). A glycogen molecule may contain more than 50,000 single glucose units and is highly branched, allowing rapid dissemination of glucose when it is needed to generate cellular energy in the body. The amount of glycogen in the body at any one time is equivalent to about 4,000 kilocalories—3,000 in muscle tissue and 1,000 in the liver.
- 3) **Building Macromolecules:** Although most absorbed glucose is used to make energy, some glucose is converted to ribose and deoxyribose, which are essential building blocks of important macromolecules, such as RNA, DNA, and ATP. Glucose is also used to produce the molecule NADPH, which is important for protecting against oxidative stress and for many other chemical reactions in the body. If all of the energy, glycogen-storing capacity, and building needs of the body are met, excess glucose can be used to make fat.
- 4) **Sparing Protein:** When there is not enough glucose to meet the body's needs, glucose is synthesized from amino acids. Because there is no storage molecule for amino

acids, this process requires the destruction of proteins, primarily from muscle tissue. The presence of adequate glucose basically spares the breakdown of proteins from being used to make the glucose the body needs.

2.8.5 GLUCOSE REGULATION

Blood sugar regulation is the process by which the body maintains blood glucose levels within a narrow range. This tight regulation is called glucose homeostasis.

GLUCOSE HOMEOSTASIS

Plasma glucose concentration is a function of the rate of glucose entering the circulation (glucose appearance) balanced by the rate of glucose removal from the circulation (glucose disappearance). Circulating glucose is derived from three sources: intestinal absorption during the fed state, glycogenolysis, and gluconeogenesis. The primary determinant of how quickly glucose appears in the circulation during the fed state is gastric emptying rate. Other sources of circulating glucose are derived chiefly from hepatic processes: glycogenolysis, the breakdown of glycogen, the polymerized storage form of glucose; and gluconeogenesis, the formation of glucose primarily from lactate and amino acids during the fasting state.

Glycogenolysis and gluconeogenesis are partly under the control of glucagon, a hormone produced in the α -cells of the pancreas. During the first 8–12 hours of fasting, glycogenolysis is the primary mechanism for providing glucose. Glucagon facilitates this

process, thereby promoting the appearance of glucose in the circulation. Over longer periods of fasting, glucose, produced by gluconeogenesis, is released from the liver.

Glucoregulatory hormones include insulin, glucagon, amylin, GLP-1, glucosedependent insulintropic peptide (GIP), epinephrine, cortisol, and growth hormone. Of these, insulin and amylin are derived from the β -cells, glucagon from the α -cells of the pancreas, and GLP-1 and GIP from the L-cells of the intestine.

The glucoregulatory hormones of the body are designed to maintain circulating glucose concentrations in a relatively narrow range. In the fasting state, glucose leaves the circulation at a constant rate. To keep pace with glucose disappearance, endogenous glucose production is necessary. For all practical purposes, the sole source of endogenous glucose production is the liver. Renal gluconeogenesis contributes substantially to the systemic glucose pool only during periods of extreme starvation. Although most tissues have the ability to hydrolyze glycogen, only the liver and kidneys contain glucose-6phosphatase, the enzyme necessary for the release of glucose into the circulation. In the bi-hormonal model of glucose homeostasis, insulin is the key regulatory hormone of glucose disappearance, and glucagon is a major regulator of glucose appearance. After reaching a post-meal peak, blood glucose slowly decreases during the next several hours, eventually returning to fasting levels. In the immediate post-feeding state, glucose removal into skeletal muscle and adipose tissue is driven mainly by insulin. At the same time, endogenous glucose production is suppressed by;

- 1) the direct action of insulin, delivered via the portal vein, on the liver, and
- 2) the paracrine effect or direct communication within the pancreas between the α - and β cells, which results in glucagon suppression (Wallum *et al.*, 1992).

2.8.6 GLUCOSE METABOLISM

Glucose metabolism involves multiple processes, including glycolysis, gluconeogenesis, glycogenolysis, and glycogenesis. Glycolysis in the liver is a process that involves various enzymes that encourage glucose catabolism in cells.

One enzyme, in particular, glucokinase, allows the liver to sense serum glucose levels and utilize glucose when they rise, for example, after eating. During periods of fasting, when there is no glucose consumption, for example, overnight while asleep, the process of gluconeogenesis takes place.

Gluconeogenesis happens when there is glucose synthesis from non-carbohydrate components in the mitochondria of liver cells. Additionally, during fasting, the pancreas secretes glucagon, which initiates glycogenolysis. In glycogenolysis, glycogen, the stored form of glucose, is broken down into glucose. The process of synthesizing glycogen is termed glycogenesis and occurs when excess carbohydrates exist in the liver (Kang *et al.*, 2016)

Glucose tolerance is regulated by the circadian cycle. In the morning, humans typically have their peak glucose tolerance for metabolism. Afternoon and evenings are a trough for

oral glucose tolerance. This trough likely occurs because pancreatic beta-cells are also most responsive in the morning—similarly, glycogen storage components peak in the evening. Adipose tissue is most sensitive to insulin in the afternoon. The varied timings of fuel utilization throughout the day compose the cycle of glucose metabolism (Poggiogalle et al., 2018).

2.8.6.1 GLYCOLYSIS

The main pathway for glucose catabolism is glycolysis, also known as the Embden–Meyerhof pathway. In this metabolic pathway, a glucose molecule is cleaved into two pyruvate molecules, and energy is produced. The process can be accomplished in the absence of oxygen (under anaerobic conditions). In aerobic organisms, glycolysis is the first part of glucose catabolism. The pyruvate produced continues oxidative degradation into CO₂ and H₂O. However, in aerobic organisms, when the oxygen supply to a tissue is insufficient (e.g., in skeletal muscle during intense exercise), pyruvate is converted to lactate via lactic acid fermentation.

The chemical transformations during glycolysis include changes in the original substrate (glucose), leading to the production of energy-rich metabolites that can transfer phosphoryl groups to ADP. This ability to generate ATP via substrate-level phosphorylation mechanisms, without oxygen or the respiratory chain, makes glycolysis highly relevant to physiological processes. The series of reactions in the glycolytic pathway can be divided into two phases. In the first phase, glucose undergoes two phosphorylation steps and is

split into two triose phosphate molecules. This is a preliminary phase during which energy is expended to form compounds that cannot escape the cell; they are chemically more reactive than glucose and can more readily undergo subsequent transformations. The result of the first set of reactions is the breakdown of the initial six-carbon molecule into two three-carbon molecules: glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate (G3P) and dihydroxyacetone phosphate (DHAP). DHAP is then converted to G3P; therefore, each glucose molecule entering glycolysis is broken down into two G3P molecules.

In the second part, glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate undergoes oxidation and redistribution of its atoms to form high-energy intermediates, which are used to synthesize ATP through substrate-level phosphorylation. This is the energy-producing stage of the pathway. All the enzymes involved in glycolysis are found in the cytosol, so the pathway occurs in the cytoplasm.

Functional Role of Glycolysis

- Skeletal muscle uses glycolysis for the generation of ATP during intense exercise. At rest or during light activity, muscle uses oxidative pathways, which yield higher ATP levels. During intense activity, glycolysis is the primary source of energy for the muscle.
- Adipose tissue is specialized in storing triglycerides. A significant function of glycolysis in adipocytes is to provide DHAP, a precursor used in triglyceride synthesis.

- Red blood cells lack mitochondria and, therefore, cannot generate ATP by oxidative pathways. They depend entirely on glycolysis for ATP synthesis. 2,3-Bisphosphoglycerate, an important modulator of hemoglobin, is generated from 1,3-bisphosphoglycerate, a metabolite of glycolysis. (Blanco & Blanco, 2017)

2.8.6.2 GLYCOGENESIS

Glycogenesis is the process of glycogen synthesis, in which glucose molecules are added to chains of glycogen for storage. This process is activated during rest periods following the Cori cycle, in the liver, and is also activated by insulin in response to high glucose levels (Patino & Orrick, 2021)

- Glucose is converted into glucose 6-phosphate by the action of glucokinase or hexokinase with the conversion of ATP to ADP.
- Glucose-6-phosphate is converted into glucose-1-phosphate by the action of phosphoglucomutase, passing through the obligatory intermediate glucose-1,6-bisphosphate.
- Glucose-1-phosphate is converted into UDP-glucose by the action of the enzyme UDP-glucose pyrophosphorylase. Pyrophosphate is formed, which is later hydrolysed by pyrophosphatase into two phosphate molecules.
- The enzyme glycogenin is needed to create initial short glycogen chains, which are then lengthened and branched by the other enzymes of glycogenesis. Glycogenin, a homodimer, has a tyrosine residue on each subunit that serves as the anchor for the

reducing end of glycogen. Initially, about seven UDP-glucose molecules are added to each tyrosine residue by glycogenin, forming $\alpha(1\rightarrow4)$ bonds.

- Once a chain of seven glucose monomers is formed, glycogen synthase binds to the growing glycogen chain and adds UDP-glucose to the 4-hydroxyl group of the glucosyl residue on the non-reducing end of the glycogen chain, forming more $\alpha(1\rightarrow4)$ bonds in the process.
- Branches are made by glycogen branching enzyme (also known as amylo $\alpha(1:4)\rightarrow\alpha(1:6)$ transglycosylase, which transfers the end of the chain onto an earlier part via α -1:6 glycosidic bond, forming branches, which further grow by addition of more α -1:4 glycosidic units.

2.8.6.3 GLYCOGENOLYSIS

Glycogenolysis is the breakdown of glycogen (n) to glucose-1-phosphate and glycogen (n-1). Glycogen branches are catabolized by the sequential removal of glucose monomers via phosphorolysis, by the enzyme glycogen phosphorylase (Nelson & Cox, 2008).

The overall reaction for the breakdown of glycogen to glucose-1-phosphate is

Here, glycogen phosphorylase cleaves the bond linking a terminal glucose residue to a glycogen branch by substitution of a phosphoryl group for the $\alpha[1\rightarrow4]$ linkage (Nelson &

Cox, 2008). Glucose-1-phosphate is converted to glucose-6-phosphate (which often ends up in glycolysis) by the enzyme phosphoglucomutase (Nelson & Cox, 2008).

Glucose residues are phosphorolysed from branches of glycogen until four residues before a glucose that is branched with an $\alpha[1\rightarrow6]$ linkage. Glycogen debranching enzyme then transfers three of the remaining four glucose units to the end of another glycogen branch.

This exposes the $\alpha[1\rightarrow6]$ branching point, which is hydrolysed by $\alpha[1\rightarrow6]$ glucosidase, removing the final glucose residue of the branch as a molecule of glucose and eliminating the branch. This is the only case in which a glycogen metabolite is not glucose-1-phosphate. The glucose is subsequently phosphorylated to glucose-6-phosphate by hexokinase (Nelson & Cox, 2008).

Glycogenolysis occurs in muscle and liver cells in response to hormonal and neural signals. In particular, glycogenolysis plays an important role in the fight-or-flight response and in regulating blood glucose levels.

Glycogenolysis is regulated hormonally in response to blood sugar levels by glucagon and insulin, and stimulated by epinephrine during the fight-or-flight response. Insulin potently inhibits glycogenolysis (Sargsyan & Herman, 2019).

In myocytes, glycogen degradation may also be stimulated by neural signals (Lodish *et al.*, 2007).

2.8.7 GLUCOSE UTILISATION

The following are the critical steps in the utilization of glucose at the cellular level-

- *Transport of glucose through the cell membrane*

For glucose to be utilized by most tissue cells, it must be transported across the cell membrane into the cytoplasm. Glucose cannot readily diffuse through because of its high molecular weight. Transport is made possible by protein carrier molecules; this is known as facilitated diffusion and occurs down the concentration gradient from high to low. There is an exception for the gastrointestinal tract and renal tubules. Here, glucose is actively transported by sodium-glucose co-transport against its concentration gradient.

- *Role of insulin in glucose metabolism*

The rate of glucose/carbohydrate utilization is under the control of the rate of insulin secretion from the pancreas. Usually, the amount of glucose that can diffuse into cells is limited, except in liver and brain cells. This diffusion is significantly increased by insulin to 10 times or more.

- *Phosphorylation of glucose*

As soon as glucose enters the cell, it becomes phosphorylated to glucose-6-phosphate. This reaction is mediated by glucokinase in the liver and hexokinase in most other cells. This phosphorylation step captures glucose inside the cell. It is primarily irreversible, except in

liver, intestinal, and renal tubular epithelial cells, where glucose phosphatase is present, making it reversible.

This glucose can then be utilized immediately for energy release through glycolysis, a multi-step process that produces ATP, or stored as glycogen (a polysaccharide). Liver and muscle cells store large amounts of glycogen for later utilization by glycogenolysis, i.e., the breakdown of glycogen to release glucose (Taneera *et al.*, 2019).

2.9 INSULIN

2.9.1 DISCOVERY OF INSULIN

In 1889, German scientists Minkowski and von Mering reported, based on their experimental work with animals, that total pancreatectomy led to the development of severe diabetes (Bliss, 1993). They hypothesised that a substance secreted by the pancreas was responsible for metabolic control. Others later refined this hypothesis, noting that diabetes is associated with the destruction of the islets of Langerhans. While Minkowski, as well as Zuelzer in Germany and Scott in the USA, attempted, with inconsistent results, to isolate and administer the missing pancreatic islet substance, Belgian investigator de Meyer in 1909 proposed the name “insulin”, as did British researcher Schaefer in 1916. Finally, in 1921, a decade later, insulin was isolated, purified, and available in a form capable of therapeutic administration.

2.9.2 STRUCTURE AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF INSULIN

A single protein (monomer) of human insulin is composed of 51 and has a molecular mass of 5808 Da. The molecular formula of human insulin is $C_{257}H_{383}N_{65}O_{77}S_6$ (Insulin human, 2019). It is a combination of two peptide chains (a dimer) called an A-chain and a B-chain, linked by two disulfide bonds. The A-chain is composed of 21 amino acids, while the B-chain consists of 30 residues. Its isoelectric point is pH 5.5 (Watkins, 1998).

The linking (interchain) disulfide bonds are formed at cysteine residues between the positions A7-B7 and A20-B19. There is an additional (intrachain) disulfide bond within the A-chain between cysteine residues at positions A6 and A11. The A-chain exhibits two α -helical regions at A1-A8 and A12-A19, which are antiparallel. At the same time, the B chain has a central α -helix (covering residues B9-B19) flanked by the disulfide bond on either side and two β -sheets (covering B7-B10 and B20-B23) (Weiss *et al.*, 2000; Fu *et al.*, 2013).

Insulin is produced and stored in the body as a hexamer (a unit of six insulin molecules), while the active form is the monomer. The hexamer is about 36000 Da in size. The six molecules are linked together as three dimeric units to form a symmetrical molecule. An important feature is the presence of zinc atoms (Zn^{2+}) on the axis of symmetry, which are surrounded by three water molecules and three histamine residues at position B10 (Weiss *et al.*, 2000; Fu *et al.*, 2013).

The hexamer is an inactive form with long-term stability that helps protect insulin's high reactivity while keeping it readily available. The hexamer-monomer conversion is a central

aspect of insulin formulations for injection. The hexamer is far more stable than the monomer, which is desirable for practical reasons; however, the monomer is a much faster-reacting drug because the diffusion rate is inversely related to particle size. A fast-acting drug means insulin injections do not have to precede mealtimes by hours, which, in turn, gives people with diabetes more flexibility in their daily schedules (Dunn, 2005). Insulin can aggregate and form fibrillar interdigitated betasheets. This can cause injection and prevent the storage of insulin for extended periods (Ivanova *et al.*, 2009)

2.9.3 SYNTHESIS AND SECRETION

Insulin is coded on the short arm of chromosome 11 (Schröder & Zühlke, 1982) and synthesised in the β cells of the pancreatic islets of Langerhans as its precursor, proinsulin. Proinsulin is synthesised in the ribosomes of the rough endoplasmic reticulum (RER) from mRNA as pre-proinsulin. Pre-proinsulin is formed by sequential synthesis of a signal peptide, the B chain, the connecting (C) peptide and then the A chain comprising a single chain of 100 amino acids. Removal of the signal peptide forms proinsulin, which acquires its characteristic 3 dimensional structure in the endoplasmic reticulum. Secretory vesicles transfer proinsulin from the RER to the Golgi apparatus, whose aqueous zinc and calcium rich environment favours formation of soluble zinc-containing proinsulin hexamers. (Dodson and Steiner, 1998). As immature storage vesicles form from the Golgi, enzymes acting outside the Golgi convert proinsulin to insulin and C-peptide (Malaisse, 1997). Insulin forms zinc-containing hexamers which are *insoluble*, precipitating as chemically stable crystals at pH 5.5. When mature granules are secreted into the circulation

by exocytosis, insulin, and an equimolar ratio of C-peptide are released. Proinsulin and zinc typically comprise no more than 6% of the islet cell secretion . (Dodson and Steiner, 1998).

Insulin secretion from the islet cells into the portal veins is characteristically pulsatile, reflecting the summation of coordinate secretory bursts from millions of islet cells. An ultradian oscillatory pattern of insulin release, in addition to post-meal variation, has been reported (*Pørksen*, 2002). In response to a stimulus such as glucose, insulin secretion is characteristically biphasic, with an initial rapid phase, followed by a less intense but more sustained release of the hormone (*Bratanova-Tochkova et al.*, 2002).

2.9.3.1 FACTORS INFLUENCING INSULIN SYNTHESIS AND SECRETION

Insulin secretion may be influenced by alterations in synthesis at the level of gene transcription, translation, and post-translational modification in the Golgi as well as by factors influencing insulin release from secretory granules. Longer-term modifications may occur through influences on β -cell mass and differentiation (*Nielsen*, 2001). Given insulin's pivotal role in glucose utilisation and metabolism, it is not surprising that glucose has multiple influences on insulin biosynthesis and secretion. However, other factors, such as amino acids, fatty acids, acetylcholine, pituitary adenylate cyclase-activating polypeptide (PACAP), glucose-dependent insulintropic polypeptide (GIP), glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1), and several other agonists, also influence these processes (*Bratanova-Tochkova et al.*, 2002).

2.9.3.2 MECHANISMS OF INSULIN SECRETION

Increased levels of glucose induce the “first phase” of glucose-mediated insulin secretion by release of insulin from secretory granules in the β cell. Glucose entry into the β cell is sensed by glucokinase, which phosphorylates glucose to glucose-6-phosphate (G6P), generating ATP (De Lonlay & Saudubray, 2000). Closure of K^+ -ATP-dependent channels results in membrane depolarization and activation of voltage-dependent calcium channels, leading to an increase in intracellular calcium concentration; this triggers pulsatile insulin secretion (Soria *et al.*, 2004). Augmentation of this response occurs by both a K^+ -ATP channel-independent Ca^{2+} -dependent pathway and K^+ -ATP channel-independent Ca^{2+} -independent pathways of glucose action (Bratanova-Tochkova *et al.*, 2002).

Other mediators of insulin release include activation of phospholipases and protein kinase C (e.g., by acetylcholine), stimulation of adenylyl cyclase activity, and activation of β -cell protein kinase A, which potentiates insulin secretion. This latter mechanism may be activated by hormones, such as vasoactive intestinal peptide (VIP), PACAP, GLP-1, and GIP. These factors appear to play a significant role in the second phase of glucose-mediated insulin secretion, after refilling of secretory granules translocated from reserve pools (Bratanova-Tochkova *et al.*, 2002).

2.9.4 MECHANISMS OF INSULIN ACTION

Insulin mediates its actions through binding to insulin receptors. The insulin receptor was first characterised in 1971. It is a heterotetramer composed of two α and two β glycoprotein subunits linked by disulphide bonds and is located on the cell membrane (Kido *et al.*, 2001). The gene coding for the insulin receptor is located on the short arm of chromosome 19 (Kahn *et al.*, 1997). Insulin binds to the extracellular α subunit, triggering a conformational change that enables ATP to bind to the intracellular β subunit (Woleve, 1990). ATP binding, in turn, triggers phosphorylation of the β subunit, conferring tyrosine kinase activity. This enables the tyrosine phosphorylation of intracellular substrate proteins known as insulin-responsive substrates (IRS). The IRS can then bind other signalling molecules which mediate further cellular actions of insulin (Kido *et al.*, 2001).

There are four known specifically-named IRS proteins. IRS 1 and 2 have widely overlapping tissue distribution. IRS 1 is phosphorylated by both the insulin receptor and insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1) receptor, mediates the mitogenic effects of insulin, and couples glucose sensing to insulin secretion, with IRS 1 proposed to be the major IRS in skeletal muscle. IRS-2, proposed to be the main IRS in the liver, mediates peripheral actions of insulin and the growth of pancreatic β cells (Kido *et al.*, 2001). IRS 3 and 4 are less well characterised. IRS 3 is found only in adipose tissue, β cells, and liver, and IRS 4 in thymus, brain, and kidney (Withers & White, 2000). Phosphorylated IRS proteins bind specific src-homology-2 domain proteins (SH2), which include important enzymes such as phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase (PI 3-kinase) and phosphotyrosine phosphatase SHPTP2

(or Syp), and other proteins that lack enzymatic activity but which link IRS-1 and other intracellular signalling systems, e.g., the adaptor protein Grb2, which connects with the RAS (rat sarcoma protein) pathway.

PI 3-kinase promotes the translocation of glucose transporter proteins, glycogen, lipids, and proteins, stimulates protein synthesis, inhibits lipolysis, and controls hepatic gluconeogenesis (Burks & White, 2001). PI 3-kinase acts via serine and threonine kinases such as Akt/protein kinase B (PKB), protein kinase C (PKC), and PI-dependent protein kinases 1 & 2 (PIPK 1 & 2). The RAS pathway activates transcription factors and enhances insulin's growth-promoting actions (Kido *et al.*, 2001). Thus, broadly, PI 3-kinase mediates insulin's metabolic effects, e.g., cellular glucose uptake, while RAS mediates insulin's mitogenic effects (Kido *et al.*, 2001), together with other less well-described actions.

Action of Insulin on Carbohydrate Metabolism

Insulin acts at multiple steps in carbohydrate metabolism. Its effect on facilitated glucose diffusion into fat and muscle cells via modulation of GLUT4 translocation has been discussed. Glycogen synthesis is increased, and glycogen breakdown is decreased, by dephosphorylation of glycogen synthase and glycogen phosphorylase kinase, respectively. Glycolysis is stimulated and gluconeogenesis inhibited by the dephosphorylation of pyruvate kinase (PK) and 2,6-bisphosphate kinase. Signalling intracellular energy abundance, insulin enhances the irreversible conversion of pyruvate to acetyl-CoA by

activation of the intramitochondrial enzyme complex pyruvate dehydrogenase. Acetyl-CoA may then be directly oxidised via the Krebs' cycle, or used for fatty acid synthesis (Denton & Tavaré, 1997).

2.9.5 PHYSIOLOGICAL ROLE OF INSULIN

Insulin is the pivotal hormone regulating cellular energy supply and macronutrient balance, directing anabolic processes of the fed state (Burks & White, 2001). Insulin is essential for the intracellular transport of glucose into insulin-dependent tissues such as muscle and adipose tissue. Signalling abundance of exogenous energy, adipose tissue fat breakdown is suppressed and its synthesis promoted. In muscle cells, glucose entry enables glycogen to be synthesised and stored, and for carbohydrates, rather than fatty acids (or amino acids) to be utilised as the immediately available energy source for muscle contraction. Insulin therefore promotes glycogen and lipid synthesis in muscle cells, while suppressing lipolysis and gluconeogenesis from muscle amino acids. In the presence of an adequate supply of amino acids, insulin is anabolic in muscle (Karam, 1997).

2.10 INSULIN SENSITIVITY INDEX

Insulin resistance plays a central role in the pathophysiology of type 2 diabetes. It is tightly associated with significant public health problems, including obesity, hypertension, coronary artery disease, dyslipidemias, and a cluster of metabolic and cardiovascular abnormalities that define the metabolic syndrome (Reaven, 2005). Insulin resistance is commonly associated with visceral adiposity, glucose intolerance,

hypertension, dyslipidemia, hypercoagulable state, endothelial dysfunction, and/or elevated markers of

inflammation. Therefore, it is of great importance to develop tools for quantifying insulin sensitivity/resistance in humans that may be used to appropriately investigate the epidemiology, pathophysiological mechanisms, outcomes of therapeutic interventions, and clinical course of patients with insulin resistance (Muniyappa *et al.*, 2008).

Metabolic actions of insulin help to maintain glucose homeostasis and promote glucose utilization (Accili, 2004). Insulin increases glucose utilization in peripheral organs (e.g., skeletal muscle and adipose tissue) and suppresses hepatic glucose production (HGP) and adipose tissue lipolysis. In addition to these classical metabolic target tissues, insulin has many other important physiological targets. The maximal effect of insulin defines “insulin responsiveness,” while the insulin concentration required for a half-maximal response defines “insulin sensitivity”.

The concept of insulin resistance was proposed as early as 1936 to describe diabetic patients requiring high doses of insulin (Himsworth, 1936). Insulin resistance is typically defined as decreased sensitivity and/or responsiveness to insulin-mediated glucose disposal and/or inhibition of HGP and adipose tissue lipolysis. Rigorous evaluation of altered sensitivity and responsiveness, therefore, requires a comparison of insulin dose-response curves.

2.10.1 DIRECT MEASURES OF INSULIN SENSITIVITY

1. Hyperinsulinemic Euglycemic Glucose Clamp

PROCEDURE

The glucose clamp technique, initially developed by Andres and DeFronzo, is widely accepted as the reference standard for directly determining metabolic insulin sensitivity in humans (11). After an overnight fast, insulin is infused intravenously at a constant rate of 5-120 mU/m²/min (dose per body surface area per minute). This constant insulin infusion results in a new steady-state insulin level above the fasting level (hyperinsulinemia). As a consequence, glucose disposal in skeletal muscle and adipose tissue is increased while HGP is suppressed. Under these conditions, a bedside glucose analyzer is used to frequently monitor blood glucose levels at 5–10 min intervals. At the same time, 20% dextrose is given intravenously at a variable rate to “clamp” blood glucose concentrations in the normal range (euglycemic). A potassium phosphate infusion is also given to prevent hypokalemia resulting from hyperinsulinemia and increased glucose disposal. After several hours of constant insulin infusion, steady-state conditions are typically achieved for plasma insulin, blood glucose, and the glucose infusion rate (GIR). Assuming that the hyperinsulinemic state is sufficient to suppress hepatic glucose production completely and that there is no net change in blood glucose concentration under steady-state clamp conditions, the GIR must equal the glucose disposal rate (M). Thus, whole-body glucose disposal at a given level of hyperinsulinemia can be directly determined. M is typically normalized to body weight or fat-free mass to generate an estimate of insulin sensitivity.

Alternatively, an insulin sensitivity index derived from clamp data can be defined as $SI_{Clamp} = M/(G \times \Delta I)$, where M is normalized for G (steady-state blood glucose concentration) and ΔI (difference between fasting and steady-state plasma insulin concentrations) (Katz *et al.*, 2000).

The validity of glucose clamp measurements of insulin sensitivity depends on achieving steady-state conditions. “Steady-state” is often defined as a period greater than 30 minutes (at least one hour after initiation of insulin infusion) during which the coefficient of variation for blood glucose, plasma insulin, and GIR is less than 5% (Chen *et al.*, 2005). It is possible to use a stable isotope or radio-labeled glucose tracer under clamp conditions to estimate HGP so that appropriate corrections can be made to M if HGP is not completely suppressed (Finegood *et al.*, 1987).

An alternative approach is to use an insulin infusion rate sufficiently high to completely suppress HGP, based on the insulin sensitivity/resistance of the population being studied. M is routinely obtained at a single insulin infusion rate, and comparisons between M or SI_{Clamp} across subjects are valid only if the same infusion rate is used for all subjects. When glucose tracers are used during a clamp study, they are infused at a constant rate throughout the study. HGP estimated during the last 20-30 min of the clamp reflects insulin-mediated HGP suppression and hepatic insulin sensitivity. Similarly, lipolytic rates can be assessed at baseline and during hyperinsulinemia during a clamp by using isotopic tracers (e.g., palmitate). A single or multistep hyperinsulinemic euglycemic clamp can be

used to measure adipose tissue insulin sensitivity. The linear relationship between log-transformed palmitate flux rates and plasma insulin concentrations yields an IC50 (pmol/L) for the suppression of lipolysis (Sondergaard & Jensen, 2016).

2. Insulin-Suppression Test (IST)

PROCEDURE

The insulin-suppression test, another method that directly measures metabolic insulin sensitivity/resistance, was introduced by Shen *et al.* in 1970 and subsequently modified by Harano *et al.* (1978). After an overnight fast, somatostatin (250 µg/h) or the somatostatin analogue octreotide (25 µg bolus, followed by 0.5 µg/min) (Pei *et al.*, 1994) is infused intravenously to suppress endogenous insulin and glucagon secretion. Simultaneously, insulin (25 mU/m²/min) and glucose (240 mg/m²/min) are infused into the same antecubital vein over three hours. From the contralateral arm, blood samples for glucose and insulin determinations are collected every 30 min for 2.5 h, then at 10 min intervals from 150 - 180 min of the IST. The constant infusions of insulin and glucose determine steady-state plasma insulin (SSPI) and glucose (SSPG) concentrations. The steady-state period is assumed to be 150-180 min after initiation of the IST. SSPI concentrations are generally (but not always) similar among subjects. Therefore, the SSPG concentration will be higher in insulin-resistant subjects and lower in insulin-sensitive subjects. That is, SSPG values are inversely related to insulin sensitivity. The IST provides a direct measure (SSPG) of

the ability of exogenous insulin to mediate the disposal of an intravenous glucose load under steady-state conditions, with endogenous insulin secretion suppressed.

2.10.2 INDIRECT MEASURES OF INSULIN SENSITIVITY

3. Minimal Model Analysis of Frequently Sampled Intravenous Glucose Tolerance Test (FSIVGTT) PROCEDURE

The minimal model, developed by Bergman, Cobelli, and colleagues in 1979, provides an indirect measure of metabolic insulin sensitivity/resistance based on glucose and insulin data obtained during an FSIVGTT (Bergman *et al.*, 1987). After an overnight fast, an intravenous bolus of glucose (0.3 g/kg body weight) is infused over 2 min starting at time 0. Currently, a modified FSIVGTT is used, in which exogenous insulin (4 mU/kg/min) is infused over 5 min, beginning 20 min after the intravenous glucose bolus (Saad *et al.*, 1997).

Some studies use tolbutamide instead of insulin in the modified FSIVGTT to stimulate endogenous insulin secretion (Yang *et al.*, 1987). Blood samples are taken for plasma glucose and insulin measurements at -10, -1, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 12, 14, 16, 20, 22, 23, 24, 25, 27, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, 100, 120, 160, and 180 min. These data are then subjected to minimal model analysis using the computer program MINMOD to generate an index of insulin sensitivity (S_I).

The minimal model is defined by two coupled differential equations with four model parameters. The first equation describes plasma glucose dynamics in a single compartment.

The second equation describes insulin dynamics in a “remote compartment”. The structure of the minimal model allows MINMOD to uniquely identify model parameters that determine a best fit to glucose disappearance during the modified FSIVGTT. S_I is calculated from two of these model parameters and is defined as fractional glucose disappearance per insulin concentration unit. In addition to S_I , other minimal model parameters may be used to estimate a “glucose effectiveness” index (S_G). S_G is defined as the ability of glucose *per se* to promote its own disposal and inhibit HGP in the absence of an incremental insulin effect (i.e., when insulin is at basal or constant concentrations).

Recently, the minimal model has been used to assess free fatty acid (FFA) insulin sensitivity. Using a one-compartment nonlinear model of FFA kinetics during FSIVGTT showed that the FFA insulin sensitivity parameter correlated well with minimal model indices (Stefanovski *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, this model also showed that glucose modulates the disposal of FFAs.

2.10.3 SIMPLE SURROGATE INDEXES FOR INSULIN SENSITIVITY/RESISTANCE

4. Surrogates Derived from Fasting Steady-state Conditions

After an overnight fast, a single blood sample is taken to determine blood glucose and plasma insulin levels. In healthy humans, the fasting state represents a basal steady state in which glucose is homeostatically maintained within the normal range, so that insulin levels do not change significantly and HGP remains constant. That is, basal insulin secretion by

pancreatic β cells determines a relatively constant level of insulinemia, which is higher or lower depending on insulin sensitivity/resistance, such that HGP matches whole-body glucose disposal under fasting conditions. Surrogate indices based on fasting glucose and insulin concentrations reflect primarily hepatic insulin sensitivity/resistance.

However, under most conditions, hepatic and skeletal muscle insulin Sensitivity and resistance are inversely proportional. In the diabetic state with fasting hyperglycemia, fasting insulin levels are inappropriately low and insufficient to maintain euglycemia. Therefore, definitions of the more useful surrogate indices take these considerations into account. Due to the lack of a standardized insulin assay, it is not possible to use surrogate indices to define universal cutoff points for insulin resistance.

5. The Homeostasis Model Assessment (HOMA)

HOMA, developed in 1985, is a model of glucose-insulin dynamics that is used to predict fasting steady-state glucose and insulin concentrations across a wide range of insulin resistance and β -cell function (Matthews *et al.*, 1985). The model assumes a feedback loop between the liver and β -cell (Wallace *et al.*, 2004); insulin-dependent HGP regulates glucose concentrations, while insulin levels depend on the pancreatic β -cell response to glucose.

Thus, deficient β -cell function reflects a diminished response to glucose-stimulated insulin secretion. Likewise, insulin resistance is reflected by the diminished suppressive effect of insulin on HGP. The HOMA model describes glucose-insulin homeostasis using a set of

empirically derived nonlinear equations. The model predicts fasting steady-state plasma glucose and insulin levels for any given combination of pancreatic β -cell function and insulin sensitivity. Computer simulations have been used to generate a grid from which mathematical transformations of fasting glucose and insulin β -cell function can be derived. (HOMA %B) from steady-state conditions. An important caveat for HOMA is that it imputes dynamic β -cell function (i.e., glucose-stimulated insulin secretion) from fasting steady-state data. In the absence of dynamic data, it is difficult, if not impossible, to determine the true dynamic function of β -cell insulin secretion.

In practice, most studies using HOMA employ a simple equation to derive a surrogate index of insulin resistance. This is defined by the product of the fasting glucose and fasting insulin divided by a constant. Thus,

$$\text{HOMA-IR} = \text{fasting insulin } (\mu\text{U/ml}) \times \text{fasting glucose (mmol/l)} / 22.5.$$
 The constant is a normalizing factor, the product of fasting plasma insulin (5 $\mu\text{U/mL}$) and plasma glucose (4.5 mmol/L), obtained from an “ideal” and “normal” individual. Therefore, for an individual with normal insulin sensitivity, $\text{HOMA-IR} = 1$. It is important to note that over wide ranges of insulin sensitivity/resistance, Log (HOMA-IR) (which normalizes the skewed distribution of fasting insulin values) determines a much stronger linear correlation with glucose clamp estimates of insulin sensitivity (Katz *et al.*, 2000). HOMA (HOMA-IR) is widely used in extensive epidemiological studies, prospective clinical trials, and clinical research (Wallace *et al.*, 2004). In research settings where assessing insulin

sensitivity/resistance is of secondary interest or where feasibility issues preclude the use of a glucose clamp, it may be appropriate to use Log (HOMA-IR). However, as discussed below, other surrogate indices have certain advantages over HOMA or Log (HOMA) in some circumstances.

6. Quantitative Insulin Sensitivity Check Index (QUICKI)

QUICKI is an empirically-derived mathematical transformation of fasting blood glucose and plasma insulin concentrations that provides a reliable, reproducible, and accurate index of insulin sensitivity with excellent positive predictive power (Chen *et al.*, 2005). Since fasting insulin levels have a non-normal skewed distribution, log transformation improves their linear correlation with SI_{clamp} . However, as with $1/(\text{fasting insulin})$ and the G/I ratio, this correlation is not maintained in diabetic subjects with fasting hyperglycemia and impaired β -cell function that is insufficient to maintain euglycemia. To accommodate these clinically important circumstances where fasting glucose is inappropriately high and insulin is inappropriately low, the addition of $\log(\text{fasting glucose})$ to $\log(\text{fasting insulin})$ provides a reasonable correction such that the linear correlation with SI_{clamp} is maintained in both diabetic and non-diabetic subjects. The reciprocal of this sum yields a further transformation of the data, generating an insulin sensitivity index that shows a positive correlation with SI_{clamp} .

Thus, $QUICKI = 1/(\text{Log}(\text{Fasting Insulin, } \mu\text{U/ml}) + \text{Log}(\text{Fasting Glucose, mg/dl}))$. Over a wide range of insulin sensitivity/resistance, QUICKI has a substantially better linear

correlation with SI_{clamp} ($r \approx 0.8 - 0.9$) than SI derived from the minimal model or HOMA-IR (Mather *et al.*, 2001). Log (HOMA) is roughly comparable to QUICKI in this regard. Multiple independent studies find excellent linear correlations between QUICKI and glucose clamp estimates (either GIR or SI_{Clamp}) in healthy subjects, obesity, diabetes, hypertension, and many other insulin-resistant states (Yokoyama *et al.*, 2004). QUICKI is among the most thoroughly evaluated and validated surrogate indices for insulin sensitivity. As a simple, practical, inexpensive, and minimally invasive surrogate for glucose clamp-derived measures of insulin sensitivity, QUICKI is appropriate and effective for extensive epidemiological or clinical research studies, for following changes after therapeutic interventions, and for studies where evaluation of insulin sensitivity is not the primary focus.

2.11 STREPTOZOTOCIN

Streptozotocin (STZ) is an antibiotic that induces β -cell destruction in pancreatic islets and is widely used experimentally to model type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM).

2.11.1 HISTORY

Streptozotocin (STZ) was initially isolated from *Streptomyces achromogenes* in 1960, with its diabetogenic properties not described until 1963 (Rakieten *et al.*, 1963). This action was characterized by Junod *et al.* (1969) based on earlier work (Junod *et al.*, 1967) showing that the diabetogenic effects are due to selective destruction of pancreatic islet β cells. As a result of this action, the animals experience insulin deficiency, hyperglycemia,

polydipsia, and polyuria, all of which are characteristic of human type 1 diabetes mellitus (T1DM; Ozougwu, 2013).

Several animal species, including the mouse, rat, and monkey, are sensitive to the pancreatic β -cell cytotoxic effects of STZ, with the rabbit being less so (Lazar et al., 1968). Currently, STZ is most often used to induce diabetes in rats and mice.

2.11.2 USES

STZ has antibiotic and antineoplastic properties. It is used to treat metastatic cancer of the pancreatic islets, and, due to its high toxicity to beta cells, it has also been widely used in scientific research to induce insulinitis and diabetes in experimental animals. It is typically prepared immediately prior to a procedure and most commonly prepared as a solution for injection. STZ is active in Hodgkin's disease, other lymphomas, and related malignancies.

2.11.3 MECHANISMS OF STREPTOZOTOCIN ACTION

STZ is a broad-spectrum antibiotic produced by the bacterium *Streptomyces achromogens*⁸. It contains a glucose molecule linked to a highly reactive methyl-nitrosourea moiety that is thought to exert STZ's cytotoxic effects. In contrast, the glucose moiety directs the chemical to the pancreatic β cells⁸. STZ has a short half-life due to rapid hepatic metabolism and renal excretion. Once STZ is eliminated from the body, further functional impairment of the liver or the kidney may be attributed to the effects of diabetic hyperglycemia. This is the basis for studying the mechanisms of STZ diabetic complications in these organs, as well as other organs such as the brain, the heart, and the muscles

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 MATERIALS

Weighing scale

Oral cannula

Needle and syringe (2ml and 5ml)

Dissecting the set and board

Centrifuge

Plain bottles

Universal or organ bottles

Fluoride oxidate

Beakers

Funnel

Spatula

Water bath

An electric analytical and precision balance

On Call plus glucometer

On Call plus strips

Glucose kit

Insulin kit.

Watman filter paper

3.1.1 CHEMICALS AND DRUGS

Methanolic extract of *Telfairia occidentalis* leaves

Glibenclamide

Streptozotocin

Citrate buffer

Distilled water

Methylated spirit

Phosphate buffer saline (PBS)

Diethyl ether

Di sodium hydrose phosphate

Mono sodium hydrose phosphate

Methanol

N-hexane

3.1.2 OTHER MATERIALS

Tissue paper

Cotton wool

Hand gloves

Face mask

Drinking and feeding troughs

Properly ventilated cages

Rat feed (grower's meal).

3.2 METHODS

3.2.1 PREPARATION OF METHANOLIC EXTRACT OF *TELFARIA OCCIDENTALIS* (T.O) LEAVES AND STOCK SOLUTION.

The fresh leaves of *Telfairia occidentalis* (TO) were obtained directly from a farmer at Mandate farm, Old Eid Road, Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria. The plant sample was prepared and taken to the Herbarium Unit, Department of Plant Biology, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria, for identification and authentication.

The identified *Telfairia occidentalis* leaves were correctly rinsed to remove soil particles and other contaminants. The plant leaves were dried to constant weight, then blended in an electric blender into a powder. The powder was stored in an airtight glass container until extraction. The powdered leaf of *Telfairia occidentalis* (1000 g) was extracted cold with 700 ml (70%) of methanol and stored at room temperature in a dark glass bottle for 72 hours. The mixture was stirred intermittently in order to achieve uniform dissolution of the powdered leaves in the solvent. After 72 hours, the mixture was sieved by muslin cloth, then decanted and filtered with Whatman filter paper (No. 1) into the glass bottles. The solution was evaporated (at 45°C) and concentrated under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator. The resultant concentrated solution was lyophilized using a freeze dryer to obtain the methanol crude extract of the leaf. The crude extract was successively extracted in order of increasing polarity by trituration with the following solvents: n-hexane, ethyl acetate, acetone, and water. Evaporation and solvent concentration were also performed to obtain the fractions. The crude and fractions of the methanol extract were put in glass containers and stored at 4°C for further processing. The percentage yield

was 20%. The stock solution for the study was prepared daily. The volume of the stock solution of *Telfairia occidentalis* extract was determined by its weight. Therefore, the volume given to each rat is determined by its weight in kilograms (kg) multiplied by the dose.

(mg/kg) divided by the concentration (mg/ml).

Mathematically:

$$\text{Volume of } Telfairia \text{ occidentalis extract (ml)} = \frac{\text{Weight of the rat (kg)} \times \text{Dose (mg/kg)}}{\text{Concentration (mg/ml)}}$$

3.2.2 CITRATE BUFFER PREPARATION

5.25 grams of citric acid and 7.35 grams of sodium citrate were dissolved in 240.75ml and 209.75ml of distilled water, respectively. The solution yielded 450 mL of citrate buffer with a pH of 4.5.

3.2.3 EXPERIMENTAL ANIMALS

Twenty-five (25) male Wistar rats weighing between 150 and 200 g were obtained from Ogbomosho in Oyo state. They were housed in a standard metabolic cage in the Central Animal House of the Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, College of Health Sciences, University of Ilorin, Nigeria. The cage was well ventilated, clean, predator-proof, in a suitable environment, and equipped with a removable waste disposal. The animal bedding was always changed to prevent the animals from feeding on it. The rats were maintained at room temperature (25 ± 20 °C) and $65 \pm 5\%$ humidity, with free access to a standard rat diet and water, which were changed daily. They were also maintained on a 12-hour

light/dark cycle. The animal feed was obtained from OgoOluwa feed, Sango, Ilorin, Kwara state. The rats were acclimatized for two weeks prior to the start of the experiment. All experiments were performed in accordance with the general rules for the care and use of laboratory animals.

3.2.4 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

The animals were treated in accordance with the University of Ilorin Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals. Also, the guiding principles for research involving animals recommended by the Declaration of Helsinki and the Guiding Principles in the care and use of animals were utilized (American Physiological Society, 2002). These guiding principles include:

- . The animals received every consideration for their comfort; they were properly housed, fed, and kept in sanitary surroundings. Appropriate anaesthetics were used to eliminate pain sensation during all surgical procedures.
- . The care and use of animals were intended to minimize discomfort and pain. All measures to minimize pain and distress that would not compromise experimental results were employed.
- . All work was under the direct supervision of an experienced investigator (research supervisor).

Ethical approval for the research was obtained from the University of Ilorin Ethical Review Committee through the Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences.

3.2.5 INDUCTION OF DIABETES MELLITUS

Diabetes mellitus was induced using intraperitoneal injection of 50mg/kg of streptozotocin (STZ). Streptozotocin was dissolved in 0.1 moldm⁻³ of sodium citrate buffer at pH 4.5 (Zafar *et al.*, 2009). The control group animals were not injected. The rats were fasted overnight before STZ administration. Seventy-two hours after streptozotocin injection, the rats were fasted for 12 hours, and blood was collected from the tail vein. After 7 days of STZ injection, the blood was re-evaluated, and persistent hyperglycemia was confirmed. Persistent hyperglycemic rats with blood glucose levels \geq 200 mg/dl were used in the experiment.

3.2.6 EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

The twenty-five (25) male Wistar rats were divided into five (5) groups, with five (5) rats in each group. The groups were labelled A-E. Administration of the methanolic extract of *Telfairia occidentalis* (METO) was given orally via an oral cannula at 9:00 a.m. -10:00 a.m. daily for 7 days.

Group A (Normal control): All the rats in this group served as controls and received 1ml/kg of distilled water for 7 days.

Group B (Diabetic control): All the rats in this group served as the diabetic (negative) control and received 1ml/kg of distilled water for 7 days.

Group C (Positive control): All rats in this group served as the positive control and received oral standard drug (Glibenclamide) at a dose of 5 mg/kg body weight for 7 days.

Group D (200mg/kg/7days): Each rat in this group received oral METO at a dose of 200 mg/kg body weight for 7 days.

Group E (600mg/kg/7 days): Each rat in this group received oral METO at a dose of 600 mg/kg body weight for 7 days.

3.2.7 WEIGHT DETERMINATION

The animals' initial weights were measured and recorded. Subsequently, the animals' weights were measured daily before administration. The weight was also measured before sacrifice. The weight of the animals was usually measured using the weighing scale.

3.2.8 ANIMAL SACRIFICE

After 7 days of administration, the rats were sacrificed the following day after an overnight fast. Diethyl ether was administered to each rat. The blood sample was collected into Heparinized bottles mainly through cardiac puncture. The abdominal cavity was opened up through a midline abdominal incision.

3.2.9 LIVER / TOTAL BODY WEIGHT DETERMINATION

Liver tissues from each animal were isolated and weighed after sacrifice. The determination of the liver/ total body weight ratio for each animal followed this.

3.2.10 BLOOD COLLECTION

At the end of the experiment, the rats were sacrificed through the use of an anaesthetic agent, ketamine hydrochloride, of which 0.2ml was administered to each rat. The blood sample was collected into EDTA and Heparin bottles, mainly from a cardiac puncture.

3.2.11 BLOOD SERUM COLLECTION

The blood samples collected into Heparin bottles were centrifuged using a macro-haematocrit centrifuge at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes, after which the serum was collected into plain bottles using a syringe. It was then taken to the laboratory for analysis.

3.2.13 PROCEDURE FOR GLUCOSE ASSAY

Principle

Enzymatic colourimetric determination of glucose involves the oxidation of glucose catalyzed by glucose oxidase; thus, the procedure is known as the glucose oxidase test. The reaction produces gluconic acid and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2). H_2O_2 is oxidatively coupled with chromogen (4-amino antipyrine and phenol) in the presence of peroxidase. This yields a red quinoneimine dye, for which the absorbance can be measured at 505nm. The absorbance at 505nm is proportional to the concentration of glucose in the sample.

Calculation for the End Point

These were calculated using the following formula;

$$\text{Glucose Conc. (ml/dl)} = \frac{\text{Absorbance of sample}}{\text{Absorbance of Standard (Trinder } et al., 1969)}} \times 100$$

*Absorbance of glucose in the serum samples and the standard was read using a micropipette reader. The value obtained for each sample was multiplied by 5.5/standard absorbance to obtain the corresponding serum glucose concentration in mmol/L.

3.2.14 PROCEDURE FOR INSULIN ASSAY PRINCIPLE OF THE TEST

The insulin ELISA uses a solid-phase sandwich method. The samples and conjugate reagent (anti-insulin biotin and HRP) are added to the wells coated with streptavidin. Insulin in the patient's serum binds to the matched pair Abs, forming a sandwich complex, and, simultaneously, the complex is immobilized on the plate via streptavidin-biotin interactions. The unbound protein and HRP conjugate are washed off during a washing step. Upon addition of the substrate, the color intensity is proportional to the insulin concentration in the samples. A standard curve is prepared by relating the color intensity to insulin concentration.

ASSAY PROCEDURE

Prior to assay, the reagents were allowed to stand at room temperature.

1. The desired number of coated strips was placed into the holder
2. 25 μ l of insulin standards, control, and patients' sera were pipetted into the appropriate wells
3. 100 μ l of working insulin enzyme conjugate was added to all wells.
4. It was thoroughly mixed for 10 seconds
5. It was incubated for 60 minutes at room temperature (18- 260C)
6. Liquid was removed from all wells, and wells were washed with 300 μ l of 1x wash buffer. It was then blotted on absorbent paper towels.
7. 100 μ l of TMB substrate was added to all wells.
8. It was incubated for 15 minutes at room temperature

9. 50 μ l of stop solution was added to all wells. The plate was shaken gently to mix the solution.

10. Absorbance was read on the ELISA Reader at 450 nm within 15 minutes after adding the stopping solution.

3.2.15 STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

Data was presented as mean \pm standard error of mean (S.E.M) and analyzed with one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by a post-Hoc Least Significance Difference (LSD) test for multiple comparisons using IBM SPSS Statistics version 20 for windows (International Business Machines Corporation, Armonk, New York, U.S). 95% level of significant ($p < 0.05$) or less were considered statistically significant.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 RESULTS

4.1 EFFECTS OF METHANOL EXTRACT OF *TELFAIRIA OCCIDENTALIS* ON GLUCOSE

The effects of the methanol extract of *Telfairia Occidentalis* leaves on plasma glucose levels in rats are shown in Table 4.1.

Untreated diabetic rats (194.1 ± 21.10 mg/dL) and diabetic treated rats (200 mg/kg of METO (155.6 ± 31.93 mg/dL), 600 mg/kg of METO (198.5 ± 9.24 mg/dL) and 5 mg/kg of Glibenclamide (196 ± 7.02 mg/dL)) had no significant difference in fasting blood glucose level compared to the control (153 ± 6.03 mg/dL).

The plasma glucose of rats treated with 200 mg/kg of METO (155.6 ± 31.93 mg/dL) was significantly lower than that of diabetic controls (194.1 ± 21.10 mg/dL). In addition, other rats had plasma concentrations similar to those in diabetic control (194.1 ± 21.10 mg/dL).

Plasma glucose levels decreased significantly in rats treated with METO at 200 mg/kg (155.6 ± 31.93 mg/dL) compared with glibenclamide-treated rats (196 ± 7.02 mg/dL).

The plasma glucose level in diabetic control rats (194.1 ± 21.10 mg/dL), glibenclamide-treated rats (196 ± 7.02 mg/dL), and those rats that received METO at 600 mg/kg (198.5 ± 9.24 mg/dL) increased significantly compared to rats that received METO at 200 mg/kg (155.6 ± 31.93 mg/dL).

Table 1: Showing results of the effects of the methanol extract of *Telfairia Occidentalis* on glucose

GROUPS	FASTING BLOOD GLUCOSE (mg/dL)
A (Normal control)	153 ± 6.03
B (Diabetic control)	194.1 ± 21.10
C (Diabetic + 5 mg/kg Of Glibenclimide)	196 ± 7.02
D (Diabetic + 200 mg/kg of METO)	155.6 ± 31.93*
E (Diabetic + 600 mg/kg of METO)	198.5 ± 9.24

4.2 EFFECTS OF METHANOL EXTRACT OF *TELFAIRIA OCCIDENTALIS* LEAVES ON TOTAL BODY WEIGHT AND LIVER - TOTAL BODY WEIGHT RATIO IN STZ-INDUCED DIABETIC WISTAR RATS.

The results of the effects of the methanol extract of *Telfairia Occidentalis* leaves on total body weight and liver-total body weight ratio are shown in Table 4.2

There was a significant increase in the liver–total body weight ratio of untreated diabetic rats (0.050 ± 0.004 g) compared to control (0.033 ± 0.004 g).

However, there was an insignificant decrease in the liver-total body weight ratio of diabetic rats treated with 600 mg/kg of METO (0.045 ± 0.003) compared to control (0.033 ± 0.004).

Table 2: Showing results of METO on total body weight and liver - total body weight ratio.

Groups	Total body weight (g)	Liver-total body weight ratio
Group A	197.6 ± 13.7	0.033 ± 0.004
Group B	197.6 ± 14.9	0.050 ± 0.004
Group C	191.8 ± 12.3	0.043 ± 0.003
Group D	188.2 ± 13.9	0.042 ± 0.003
Group E	186.5 ± 18.6	0.045 ± 0.003

4.3 EFFECTS OF METHANOL EXTRACT OF *TELFAIRIA OCCIDENTALIS* ON FASTING PLASMA INSULIN

The results of the effect of the Methanol extract of *Telfairia Occidentalis* on Fasting plasma insulin levels in STZ-induced diabetic rats are shown in Figure 4.3

The fasting plasma insulin level in untreated diabetic rats ($185.39 \pm 64.78 \mu\text{IU/mL}$) was significantly higher than in control rats ($4.31 \pm 2.05 \mu\text{IU/mL}$).

However, there was a significant decrease in diabetic rats treated with 5mg/kg of Glibenclamide, 200mg/kg of METO, and 600mg/kg of METO, respectively, when compared to the untreated diabetic rats.

Figure 2: Effects of methanol extract of *Telfairia occidentalis* on fasting plasma insulin in STZ-induced diabetic male Wistar rats. *** $P < 0.001$ vs control; ### $P < 0.001$ vs diabetic control; ### $P < 0.001$ vs diabetic control; ### $P < 0.001$ vs diabetic control.

4.4 EFFECTS OF METHANOL EXTRACT OF *TELFAIRIA OCCIDENTALIS* ON INSULIN SENSITIVITY INDEX.

The results of the effect of the Methanol extract of *Telfairia occidentalis* on the insulin sensitivity index in STZ-induced diabetic rats are shown in Figure 4.2

The insulin sensitivity index in untreated diabetic rats (0.312 ± 0.11) and diabetic rats treated with 600mg/kg of METO (0.418 ± 0.17) was significantly reduced when compared to control (0.702 ± 0.85).

However, there was a significant increase in diabetic rats treated with 5mg/kg of Glibenclamide (0.657 ± 0.30) and 200mg/kg of METO (0.829 ± 0.30), respectively, compared to untreated diabetic rats (0.312 ± 0.11).

Figure 3: Figure 4.2 Effects of methanol extract of *Telfairia occidentalis* on insulin sensitivity index in STZ-induced diabetic male Wistar rats. ** $P < 0.01$ vs control; ** $P < 0.01$ vs control; ## $P < 0.001$ vs diabetic control; ### $P < 0.001$ vs diabetic control.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 DISCUSSION

The present study showed that 200mg/kg of *Telfairia occidentalis* caused a significant reduction in fasting plasma glucose levels compared with the diabetic control after 7 days of treatment. These findings are consistent with the previously reported one-week hypoglycaemic effect by Salman et al. (2021). The decrease in blood glucose after 7 days could be due to an increase in plasma insulin following TO treatment, as observed in this experiment and previously reported (Eseyin *et al.*, 2010; Salman *et al.*, 2021). The increase in plasma insulin and consequent reduction in blood glucose caused by TO might be connected with the TO's tannins and saponins; both of which have well-documented hypoglycaemic properties (Liu *et al.*, 2003; Xu *et al.*, 2018). The observation in this study contradicts the previous findings by Salman *et al.* (2013 which observed an increased fasting plasma glucose in rats that received the same dose for the same period.

Insulin is a well-known hypoglycaemic agent that regulates glucose metabolism by direct and indirect actions. Insulin mediates its actions through binding to insulin receptors. By binding to its receptors in the liver, kidney, muscle, and adipose tissue, insulin activates its signaling pathway, which involves a complex cascade of protein kinases and regulatory proteins, of which insulin receptor substrate 1 (IRS-1) and insulin receptor substrate 2 (IRS-2) are the most important. This causes (1) suppression of glucose release from the liver and kidney (Woleve, 1990), (2) translocation of glucose transporters in muscle and adipose tissue to increase their glucose uptake (Kido *et al.*, 2001).

Furthermore, this study showed that TO increased insulin sensitivity following 200mg/kg METO administration for 7 days. This revealed upregulation of glucose receptors, leading to increased insulin responsiveness and reduced resistance in tissues such as the liver, kidney, muscle, and adipose tissue. This resulted in increased glucose utilization by the tissue cells.

Diabetes is the most common metabolic disorder that affects lipid, protein, and carbohydrate metabolism, characterized by reduced total body weight and an increase in the liver weight–total body weight ratio (Nakagawa & Maeda, 2012). This study showed that METO caused an insignificant decrease in the liver weight–total body weight ratio in diabetic rats treated with 600mg/kg METO for 7 days, compared with controls. However, there was no change in total body weight in any of the treated rats.

The results suggested that METO mediated changes that increased insulin sensitivity in tissues by upregulating glucose receptors, thereby increasing glucose utilization via insulin action on the receptors.

5.1 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study reveals that *Telfairia occidentalis* could be a promising hypoglycaemic agent, as it reduces blood glucose levels, lowers blood insulin concentration, and increases tissue sensitivity and responsiveness to insulin, thereby enhancing glucose utilisation.

5.2 RECOMMENDATION

Fluted pumpkin leaves are a highly nutritious vegetable that is predominantly grown by small-scale farmers and commonly consumed by the majority of people. It is therefore advised that;

1. Further studies should be done to identify the active ingredient in TO that is responsible for the hypoglycemic activity.
2. Further studies should be done to understand the mechanism of action of *Telfairia occidentalis*
3. The health practitioners should combine the consumption of TO with the conventional anti-diabetic drugs in the treatment of diabetes mellitus.

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